

Synthesis of some 2-Aryl-3-(2-imino-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)-thiazolidin-4-ones, 2-Aryl-3-(2-thiohydantoin-3-yl)-thiazolidin-4-ones and 2-Amino-4-arylthiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles as Possible Bactericides

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2 Aryl-3-(2-imino-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)thiazolidin-4-ones (2a-g), 2-aryl-3-(2-thiohydantoin-3-yl)thiazolidin-4-ones (3a-g) and 2-amino-4-arylthiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4a-g) have been obtained by cyclisation of 2-aryl-3-thiocarbanilido-4-thiazolidinones (1) with chloroacetic acid in methanol, pyridine and concentrated sulphuric acid respectively. All the compounds have been assayed for their antibacterial activity against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*.

THIAZOLIDINES¹, thiohydantoin² and thiadiazole³ derivatives are well-known for their varied biological activities. Therefore, it was felt interesting to bring any two of these biologically active systems within a molecular framework with a view to study their additive effects on their biological properties.

The synthon, 2-aryl-3-thiocarbanilido-4-thiazolidinone (1a-g) were employed for the preparation of all the three types of compounds. Thus 1a-g on reacting with chloroacetic acid/fused sodium acetate in methanol⁴ furnished the corresponding 2-aryl-3-(2-imino-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)thiazolidin-4-ones (2a-g). Similarly, 1a-g on treatment with chloroacetic acid in presence of pyridine⁵ furnished the 2-aryl-3-(2-thiohydantoin-3-yl)thiazolidin-4-ones (3a-g) which are isomeric to 2a-g. The absence of ν_{NH} peaks in their ir spectra suggested the cyclisation of 1a-g into 2a-g and 3a-g, respectively.

The cyclodehydration of 1a-g with concentrated sulphuric acid furnished the heterocycle 2-amino-4-aryl-thiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4a-g). The absence of $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ peak in the ir spectra of 4a-g suggested the cyclisation of 1a-g into 4a-g (Scheme 1).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer at 60 MHz.

2-Phenyl-3-thiocarbanilido-4-thiazolidinone (1a): A mixture of benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (0.01 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.01 mol) in dioxane (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The solvent was then removed and the residue was dissolved in water and

a; R=H
b; R=2-OH
c; R=4-Cl
d; R=2-Cl
e; R=3-OCH₃, 4-OH
f; R=4-N(CH₃)₂
g; R=3-NO₂

Scheme 1

neutralised with sodium bicarbonate. The resulting yellow crystalline solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (1.8 g, 72%), m.p. 142° (Found: C, 47.2; H, 4.1; N, 16.2. C₁₀H₁₁ON₃S₂ requires: C, 47.4; H, 4.3; N, 16.6%). ν_{max} (KBr) 3 450, 3 310 (NH₂), 1 110 (C=S), 1 640 (C=O), 1 530, 1 480 and 1 460 (aromatic ring); δ (60 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 3.5 (2H, s, CH₂O), 3.1 (1H, s, S-CH-N), 7.2-8.5 (5H, m, ArH); m/z 253.

Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1a	H	142	72.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ ON ₃ S ₂
1b	2-OH	209	70.8	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂
1c	4-Cl	204	76.6	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ON ₃ S ₂ Cl
1d	2-Cl	187	73.1	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ON ₃ S ₂ Cl
1e	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	181	66.6	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂
1f	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	190	72.4	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ ON ₄ S ₂
1g	3-NO ₂	207	73.3	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂
2a	H	241	68.9	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂
2b	2-OH	270	77.4	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂
2c	4-Cl	267	78.7	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl
2d	2-Cl	246	84.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl
2e	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	230	75.7	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂
2f	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	211	84.8	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂
2g	3-NO ₂	214	81.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂
3a	H	212	75.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂
3b	2-OH	234	83.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S ₂
3c	4-Cl	238	75.7	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl
3d	2-Cl	190	87.8	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂ Cl
3e	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	229	81.8	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ S ₂
3f	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	191	72.7	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S ₂
3g	3-NO ₂	210	78.7	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₄ S ₂
4a	H	158	86.9	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₃ S ₂
4b	2-OH	203	72.0	C ₁₀ H ₉ ON ₃ S ₂
4c	4-Cl	199	85.1	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₃ S ₂ Cl
4d	2-Cl	201	77.7	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₃ S ₂ Cl
4e	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OH	181	81.4	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃ S ₂
4f	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	216	74.0	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂
4g	3-NO ₂	188	85.7	C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₄ S ₂

*Satisfactory C, H and N analyses were obtained.

2-Phenyl-3-(2-imino-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl)-thiazolidin-4-one (2a): A mixture of **1a** (0.01 mol), chloroacetic acid (0.011 mol) and fused sodium acetate (0.012 mol) was refluxed in methanol for 3 h. On cooling, the solid mass was poured in cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (2.0 g, 68.9%), m.p. 241° (Found: C, 48.7; H, 3.2; N, 14.1. C₁₂H₁₁O₂N₃S₂ requires: C, 49.1; H, 3.7; N, 14.3%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (NH), 1 640 (C=O), 1 600, 1 520 and 1 460 (aromatic ring); δ (60 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 3.0 (1H, s, CH), 3.4–3.9 (4H, s, CH₂CO), 7.4–7.7 (5H, m, ArH), 8.1–8.3 (1H, h, NH); m/z 293; **2f** δ (60 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 1.3 (6H, s, CH₃), 3.0 (1H, s, CH), 3.3–3.8 (4H, s, CH₂CO), 7.0–7.6 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.8–9.0 (1H, h, NH).

Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

2-Phenyl-3-(2-thiohydantoin-3-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (3a): A mixture of monochloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) and **1a** (0.01 mol) was refluxed for ~0.5 h in pyridine (10.0 mol). The syrupy mass was treated with absolute ethanol and again refluxed for 10 min. Upon cooling, crystalline solid separated out slowly which was recrystallised from methanol, (2.2 g, 75.8%), m.p. 212° (Found: C, 48.7; H, 3.3; N, 14.0. C₁₂H₁₁O₂N₃S₂ requires: C, 49.1; H, 3.7; N, 14.3%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 420 (NH), 1 640 (C=O), 1 240 (C=S); δ (60 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 2.9 (1H, s, CH), 3.0

(2H, s, CH₂CO), 3.3 (2H, s, N-CH₂CO), 6.1–7.5 (5H, m, ArH), 9.8 (1H, s, NH); m/z 293.

Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

2-Amino-4-phenyl-thiazolo[4,3-b]-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (4a): Compound **1a** (0.01 mol) was added slowly to sulphuric acid (A.R.; 0.015 mol) in cold. The resulting mass was cooled and poured into cold water. On neutralisation with liquor ammonia, the desired solid product was obtained which was recrystallised from ethanol, (2.0 g, 86.9%), m.p. 158° (Found: C, 50.7; H, 3.2; N, 17.7. C₁₀H₉N₃S₂ requires: C, 51.1; H, 3.8; N, 17.9%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 420, 3 220 (NH₂), 1 590, 1 530 and 1 460 (aromatic rings); δ (60 MHz; DMSO-d₆) 2.8 (1H, s, CH), 4.5 (1H, s, olefinic), 7.3–7.5 (5H, m, ArH) and 8.4–8.5 (2H, s, NH₂); m/z 251.

Other compounds were prepared similarly (Table 1).

Antibacterial activity: All the compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* filter paper disc technique⁶ at 1000, 750 and 500 mg dm⁻³ concentrations.

The results reveal that all the compounds are moderately active except **3d**, **4b** and **4c**. These compounds showed maximum inhibition against *S. aureus* and *B. subtilis* at 1000 mg dm⁻³.

Compounds **4a–g** were found more active than **2a–g** and **3a–g**, while **3a–g** were more active than **2a–g**. It is to be noted that presence of substituents like Cl, OH, OCH₃, NO₂ and -N(CH₃)₂ at the phenyl ring, imparts enhanced antibacterial activity in compounds **3** and **4**.

Compound **4b** having a OH group at position-2 on the phenyl ring had activity nearly comparable to commercial antibacterial agent, tetracyclin.

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